

Jewish objects painted inside the doorway of a cubiculum in the Vigna Randanini catacomb.

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**Jewish Catacomb Bibliography
Notes 3: Elsa Laurenzi,
La Catacomba Ebraica di Vigna
Randanini, Rome, Gangemi
Editore, 2013.**

Elsa Laurenzi's presentation of the Jewish catacombs of the Vigna Randanini in Rome for the Gangemi series on "Roma Ebraica" is the first detailed archaeological

survey of the site in many generations, a fact most surprising given the catacomb's significance as one of the few material testimonies to Jews in Ancient Rome thus far revealed. As an erratically conceived though stable (and publicly accessible) series of tunnels and chambers, the cemetery has long exerted a fascination over Jews and non-Jews alike for its subterranean layout and evocative inscriptions, the majority of which are in Greek (pp. 84-85, n. 37). A comprehensive and amply illustrated account of the catacomb's excavation, design and exploitation is therefore most welcome in the same year that other important Jewish catacomb publications have been issued or are in the works.¹ That the book itself is jointly sponsored by Italy's Fine Arts Ministry and the Jewish Community of Rome (with funding provided by the Elio Toaff Foundation for Jewish Culture) is a sign of a new season of collaboration between "Synagogue and State" on the conservation of Jewish cemeteries in Italy, a legal obligation for Italy and long an issue of concern to Jews.²

The opening chapter sets the scene in the final years of the papacy's temporal power over Rome, just as a new dawn is breaking for the archaeology of the catacombs with the impending publications of Giovanni Battista de Rossi's *Roma Sotterranea Cristiana* and *Bullettino di Archeologia Cristiana*, the self-driven undertakings of their stalwart creator that will define the field for generations to come. Yet the discovery of a Jewish catacomb in 1859 is quickly disassociated from other government-sponsored work in the catacombs under the supervision of the de Rossi-dominated *Commissione di Archeologia Sacra* (CDAS) because the site contains no signs of Christian burial and is instead left in the hands of private excavators Giuseppe Randanini and Ignazio del Frate, who hope to speculate on what (and, as it turns out, primarily *who*) lies beneath the hilly

¹ Future "Jewish Catacomb Bibliography Notes" will hopefully review *La Catacomba ebraica di Monteverde: vecchi dati e nuove scoperte*, D. Rossi & M. Di Mento, eds., Rome, 2013, and an illustrated volume on the Jewish catacombs of Rome by L. V. Rutgers, in press.

² Elio Toaff did much to improve relations between the Jews of Rome and the Vatican during his momentous tenure as Chief Rabbi of Rome from 1951 to 2002, going on record in 1977 as saying it was "thanks to the Vatican" that the Jewish catacombs had been preserved (*Time Magazine*, vol. 109 n. 21 (May 23d, 1977), p. 85). His "Fondazione per la cultura ebraica" can be contacted at: <http://www.romaebraica.it/fondazione-elio-toaff/> (December 2013).

terrain on the Appian Way two and a half miles outside of Rome.³ Laurenzi notes the political situation as critical because it will prevent adequate government intervention in the tutelage of a Jewish cemetery, or any catacomb, for that matter, perceived as non-Christian or too poorly preserved. It should be added that many catacombs – not just those of the Jews – met this fate both before and after Italy’s conquest of Rome in 1870. Christian archaeology was perceived as one of the “safe” areas of scholarly inquiry into the origins of the church in Rome, but this kept de Rossi and his colleagues in a sort of “ideological cage” that restricted work on the material evidence coming to light without precedent in the building of modern Rome.⁴

Three-chambered columbarium from the era in which the Junii Silani columbarium would have been used (1st-2^d centuries CE).

In consequence of the CDAS decision in July of 1859, the dig was relegated by the Antiquities and Fine Arts Commission to a “search for antiquities” or treasure hunt rather than a serious investigation into the historical presence of Jews in Rome in Imperial times. This attitude is seen in the inspectors’ efforts to “lump” the catacomb’s preservation together with that of a three-chambered columbarium on the same property that was in good condition at the time of its discovery in 1861 and identified as a burial site for freedmen and household members of the *gens Junia* during the first and second centuries CE. Plans are made for the architect Francesco Fontana

to survey the monument to the Junii freedmen and recompense the landowners for the “small bit of property” that would have to be relinquished should the columbarium be preserved.⁵ Yet the catacomb is described by government administrator Luigi Grifi as something from which “little or no benefit to science can be made ... (and) little or nothing for the study of art”.⁶ Only decorated or inscribed artifacts from the

³ This move on the part of the CDAS is a literal interpretation of its authority: nevertheless, de Rossi, his geologist brother and colleagues from the “Accademia Prussiana” had recently attempted to penetrate into the Jewish catacombs of the Monteverde that another CDAS member, Fr. Giuseppe Marchi, S.J., had also been unable to enter in 1843: ASR, Min, LL., PP., Ind., Agr., Comm. Belle Arti, b. 430, fasc. 479a. (May 14th, 1870) & M. S. de Rossi, *Analisi Geologica ed Architettonica* in G. B. de Rossi, *Roma Sotteranea Cristiana*, Rome 1864, p 51.

⁴ Christian archaeology is grouped together with Canon Law and Liturgy as one of the “safe” sciences in mid-19th century Rome by T. Bokenkotter in *A Concise History of the Catholic Church*, rev. ed., New York, 1990, p. 278. The term for the de Rossi generation’s “confinement” within the parameters of Church teaching is from C. Carletti, *Epigrafia dei cristiani in occidente dal III al VII secolo*, Bari, 2007, p. 14.

⁵ ASR, Min, LL., PP., Ind., Agr., Comm. Belle Arti, b. 430, fasc. 1237 (February 24th, 1862). Fontana’s drawing and survey have not been published.

⁶ ASR, Min, LL., PP., Ind., Agr., Comm. Belle Arti, b. 430, fasc. 258 (January 14th, 1863). Particularly revealing is Grifi’s dry comment that “everyone has his or her own opinions on matters, even in the science of archaeology, but these must be based on facts and not on the inclinations of the spirit”, in reference to Visconti and de Rossi’s advocacy for continued access to the site. Grifi was ultimately advised by his

columbarium by virtue of its connection to “one of the most illustrious families of Ancient Rome” are recommended for purchase by the Vatican Museums.

Laurenzi does a good job of streamlining the account of the Randanini excavations from 1859-1864, which is no easy task given the masses of paperwork in the government archives often stating more or less the same thing over and over which nonetheless have to be carefully reviewed for annotations and other information that the published sources from this period do not contain. In this sense, it is both a blessing and a curse that the Randanini folder was organized as a “Vendita di oggetti d’arte” (“Sale of works of art”) rather than as one of the authorized “Scavi” (“Excavations”) when the government filed a lawsuit against the family in 1870 for the illegal sale and exportation of Jewish artifacts abroad: a blessing, because the notoriously bureaucratic system has preserved information about finds whose whereabouts are now unknown, and a curse (at least to those unfamiliar with 19th century Italian legalese), due to the circumstances noted above, and the necessity of literally reading between the lines for data of real significance. Laurenzi’s transcription of the information that these documents contain is therefore greatly appreciated. The only thing lacking, perhaps, is consistent reference to the catacomb plan published on p. 30: that is, in the account of a significant discovery like that of the three flights of stairs cited on p. 20, n. 42, it would be helpful to specify that there are the stairs marked “Aa”. It is true that some accounts are too vague to be localized with precision – like the curious report of a mosaic depicting the heads of a bearded man with a diadem and woman (p. 17, n. 30) and recovery of a chamber with “grand arched niches,” a mosaic floor and stairway (p. 20, n. 43) – but others can be identified with confidence, and can help with the reconstruction of structural features that are not visible today or have been heavily restored, like the skylight outside of two of the four chambers found on May 18th, 1862 (the chamber n. 13, preceded by a long corridor lined with plaster that was initially thought to be a room, not a hall).⁷ Cutting off this data from the topographical analysis in Chapter 2 can at times get confusing, especially when one reads on p. 16 of the discovery of a staircase to galleries below ground, discovered in 1860, but later defined as separate from the Jewish site.⁸

Randanini’s original partner, the architect and sometime antiquities dealer Ignazio del Frate, appears to have dropped out of the venture around 1862, perhaps because it was a poor investment overall in terms of returns, that is, artifacts that could fetch a good price (astonishing as it may seem, the Jewish epitaphs themselves were seen as of little value, except, of course, to “black market” collectors). Many years later, an American scholar published a series of ancient epitaphs on the property of one Gastone del Frate on Monte Mario in Rome.⁹ Every single one was listed as of unknown provenance, although

ministry to take no “definite” stand on the issue of Randanini’s compensation, which came to nothing in the end.

⁷ Laurenzi, 2013, p. 18, n. 35.

⁸ C. L. Visconti, Scavi di Vigna Rondanini, in *Bullettino dell’Istituto di Corrispondenza Archeologica*, Rome, 1861, p. 22.

⁹ Bibliography in *JWE* 2, p. 437: the majority of the inscriptions on the del Frate estate are neutral, but one (p. 76, n. 7) in Greek praises a woman as φίλανδρος (a term found in a number of Jewish funerary inscriptions from Rome: S. Cappelletti, *The Jewish Community of Rome from the Second Century BCE to the Third Century CE*, Leiden, 2006, p. 189, n. 61), a body of evidence which, as L. V. Rutgers points out in *The Jews of Late Ancient Rome*, Leiden, 1995, p. 195, nn. 56-57, includes compound terms beginning with philo- far more often (26.8%) than either the Christians (5.5%) or the pagans (3.2%). Another

it was certain that they had all come from Rome, and had arrived at the Del Frate estate “from sources not entirely free of suspicion”, that is, from tomb robbers or others who chose not to report such finds to the State. One neutral-sounding Latin inscription on a marble plaque is considered Jewish by virtue of the individuals named in the dedication, Juda and Maria (JIWE 2.553): another piece names a freedwoman of the *Junia* (Junia Onesime), that brings to mind the dozens of tituli to freedmen of the same name who were buried in a large, three-chambered columbarium in the Vigna Randanini (with some of these apparently reused in the catacomb - like JIWE 2.609, and possibly JIWE 2.610 - at a later date). However circumstantial the evidence, it is possible that the del Frate involved in the early stages of the Vigna Randanini excavations made off with a share of the finds (Randanini is suspected, in fact, of not reporting all the artifacts from the dig at the time of his collaboration with del Frate, although his son, Ignazio, later complains to de Rossi that the family, too, had been a victim of theft).¹⁰

Laurenzi notes on p. 14, n. 16 that it is not known how Rome’s Jewish community first reacted to the news of the catacomb’s discovery, although a number of Jews are recorded as having visited the site, most notably the French baron and banker James de Rothschild, who apparently entertained the notion of purchasing the property from the Randanini before his death in 1868, at least according to Randanini’s legal depositions of 1869 and 1870. Rumors of the impending sale nonetheless elaborated upon the idea that Baron de Rothschild’s ultimate refusal was on ideological grounds: namely that the catacomb was not sufficiently “Jewish” from a lack of Hebrew in the inscriptions and the presence of profane pictures and other figurative images in some of the crypts. In these aspects as well as in much of its topography it resembled a Christian site, and was therefore assumed by some to have been used by Judeo-Christians or Jewish converts to Christianity in Rome (a theory that both de Rossi and Garrucci strongly opposed).¹¹ How the baron first got hold of this notion is not clear, although the debate in Rome over the

inscription in the del Frate collection (p. 78, n. 17), concludes with the expression “Dormit in Deo”, suggestive of a Jewish or, more likely, a Christian text.

¹⁰ Laurenzi, 2013, p. 16, n. 26 & Cod. Vat. 14267, f. 178 (March 31st, 1882). In a final season of excavation in 1864, Randanini finds a sarcophagus in many pieces, decorated with an unspecified figurative scene, which he petitions to bring into Rome for repairs, with the expectation that it will later return to the site: ASR, Min, LL., PP., Ind., Agr., Comm. Belle Arti, b. 430, fasc. 789 (February 10th, 1864). Perhaps this is a reference to the “sarcophago di epoca cristiana, ma servito ad uso pagano” for sale on p. 25, n. 62. A number of sarcophagus fragments from the site were later sent (ca. 1911-1912) to the Museo Nazionale Romano.

¹¹ De Rossi’s position was that Jewish converts would have been buried with other Christians, and not separately. The perception among some Jews that the catacomb was “not Jewish enough” is reflected in a notice by T. Ratcliffe in the London journal *Long Ago: A Journal of Popular Antiquities*, 1 (1873), p. 184: “Some ten years ago a supposed Jewish cemetery or catacomb was discovered outside of Rome, about a mile from the Porta San Sebastiano, and more recently the discovery of another Jewish cemetery in a totally different quarter of the city was announced. No Hebrew inscriptions were found, all the letters being Greek, and the presumption was, that these cemeteries were used by the large colonies of Jews settled in Rome before the fall of the Empire. In noticing these discoveries the Jewish Chronicle sides with the opinion that the so-called “Jewish” catacombs are only Jewish in a certain sense—that they were the burial-places of the early Christians, who claimed to be Jews and kept the Jewish Sabbath. Tacitus and other writers always spoke of the Christians as being a sect of the Jews, and they were popularly regarded in that light, and possibly claimed to be so even when not of Jewish blood and descent. The representation of fruit, flowers, &c, on the tombs, seems a pretty conclusive proof that they could not be the burial-places of” the orthodox Jews, who had not adopted the Christian development of Judaism.”

“Jewishness” of the painted chambers was as polemical as it was personal, and might have been perceived by some Orthodox Jews as a means to intensify the attacks on their community by certain members of the Roman Catholic Church (nor did it sit well that the Jesuit Garrucci was the one chiefly responsible for the divulgation of the site, and took nearly two decades to publish a selection of the images in question).¹² Yet Rome’s Jews remained for the most part silent on the issue, to the point that an Italian Jew from the north exclaimed that they seemed to be “sleeping”!¹³ And well might they have been in this regard, for not even the intervention of a Rothschild could relieve them from harsh government reprisals following the failed revolution in Rome of 1848.

In the end, Randanini’s own downfall was not to waken the dead, so to speak, but to believe in all the hype: the visits by scholars and foreign dignitaries, the notices in the international press, and especially the encouragement of individuals like Fr. Raffaele Garrucci, who let Randanini believe he was an intermediary between the family and certain members of the Antiquities and Fine Arts Commission for a monetary reward equal to that given to another private excavator, Lorenzo Fortunati, for excavations on the third mile of the via Latina in 1858 that had brought monumental tombs, a Christian basilica to St. Stephen and a number of small catacombs to light.¹⁴ Archaeology had been a hobby for many in Rome, and an expensive one at that, but Randanini was in the unique situation of being able to excavate a catacomb because it was not a Christian site. Otherwise, he would certainly not have been allowed to keep churning up dirt in galleries long assumed to have formed part of the Christian cemetery of Callisto. Yet all the promises of financial gain were but fleeting: instead of being able to sell the Jewish pieces to museums and collectors, Randanini was told to keep everything in the catacomb right where it was (and it could not be backfilled, like the columbaria and other sepulchers he had found in the dig).

Laurenzi’s account of the excavation cites the archival documentation up to the year 1870, after which time little activity is recorded on the site (Ignazio Randanini, son of the original owner, was expressly forbidden to undertake new excavations in the catacomb when he applied for new excavation licenses in 1870 and 1874, although he was allowed to do so in other areas of the estate).¹⁵ With a lawsuit against the Randanini for the illegal sale of Jewish artifacts to the English collector Charles Willes Wilshere

¹² Garrucci, *Storia dell’ arte cristiana nei primi otto secoli della chiesa*, vol. 6, Prato, 1881, p. 489 (omitting the back panel of the inner chamber of cubiculum n. 14).

¹³ G. Levi, in *L’educatore israelita*, 21 (1873), p. 116, finds that the contradictory evidence from the site and its study and its publication by members of the Roman Catholic Church had cast much doubt on its “Jewishness”. Nevertheless, even Levi pleads for its care by modern Jews, exclaiming “Roma israelitica dorme!”

¹⁴ Laurenzi, 2013, pp. 21-23, nn. 50-53 & p. 24, n. 57. Fortunati had found many “pagan and Christian” artifacts in his excavations of 1858 that the Commissione Generale Consultiva di Belle Arti e di Antichità recommended for purchase by the Vatican Museums, with “compensation for the expenses incurred during their extraction” (ASR, Min, LL., PP., Ind., Agr., Comm. Belle Arti, b. 376). Garrucci involved himself with the situation by promising to publish a detailed “atlas” of Fortunati’s finds, that was never completed. He later publicly exhorted the government to assist Randanini with a vague reference to the discovery of a “lower floor” in his discourse to the Pontificia Accademia Romana di Archeologia on June 11th, 1862, (Garrucci, *Descrizione del cimitero ebraico di Vigna Randanini*, *Dissertazioni della Pontificia Accademia Romana di Archeologia*, 15 (1884), p. 97).

¹⁵ Laurenzi, 2013, p. 26, n. 64, plus another license granted to Ignazio Randanini on January 18th, 1874 (signed by G. Fiorelli). Agricultural work nearby brought up additional graves and artifacts in 1878.

still pending, the catacomb was apparently sealed for about a decade until the early 1880's, at which time digging in the catacomb was revived as well as family's hopes for a change of fortune.¹⁶ Clearly, then, the CDAS's renewed jurisdiction "independent and absolute" over the catacombs did not include this non-Christian site. Archaeologists Muller and Maruchi both record new Jewish inscriptions in the 1880's, but with little or no data on where or when they had been found. Indeed, following the sale of the property in a bankruptcy auction in 1896, there is a gaping hole in our knowledge of the site.¹⁷ Various individuals possessed it or attempted to do so until the unspecified time of its purchase by the Marquis Alberto del Gallo di Roccagiovine, direct descendent of one of the most illustrious 19th century archaeologists in Rome, Lucien Bonaparte, Prince of Canino, but the identity of the mysterious American noted in some early 20th century government reports as plotting to make away with important catacomb artifacts is not known, nor are the conditions under which the site's most significant find, the marble sarcophagus with Jewish ritual objects (fig. 49), was transported to the Kaiser Frederick Museum in Berlin around the year 1908 (government reports suspect the above-mentioned American, but given the piece's ultimate destination, it is also possible that Prof. Nikolaus Muller transported it to Berlin as part of his "study collection": as director of the Berlin University Museum and excavator of the Jewish catacombs of the Monteverde, he had good reason to be concerned about the fate of all the surviving Jewish artifacts in Rome).¹⁸

A century or so later, del Gallo di Roccagiovine family still owns the property, although oversight of the catacomb was handed over to the Italian state in 1986 following a new treaty between the governments of Italy and the Roman Catholic Church. Beyond the limited documentation of restoration work from the 1940's-1970's in the archives of the Pontifical Commission for Sacred Archaeology and inventories of materials for the Museo Nazionale Romano and Soprintendenza Archeologica di Roma, very little is known about the catacomb's 20th century upkeep apart from the eyewitness accounts of those with access to the site (Laurenzi quotes the longtime catacomb caretaker, Alberto Marcocci, on certain details, and it was Marcocci and another colleague who created structural reinforcements to the site in 2001).¹⁹ Yet E. R. Goodenough was able to publish sculptural fragments in 1952 that had gone unrecorded, and it would be timely to have an inventory of all such finds from the del Gallo Roccagiovine buildings and

¹⁶ The Randanini applied for a new excavation license in 1882: ACS, AA.BB.AA., 3 vers., 2 pt., b. 246, fasc. 5, n. 4269 (1882-1885). The new excavations apparently brought little new material to light (A. Berliner, *Storia degli Ebrei di Roma*, trans. A. Audisio, Milan, 1992, p. 49).

¹⁷ ACS, AA. BB. AA., 2a vers. 2a ser., b. 421: "Roma - via Appia 1882-1896. Catacombe ebraiche nella Vigna Randanini. Epigrafia, permessi di scavo, vendita' giudiziale del fondo."

¹⁸ Laurenzi notes on p. 26 that the property was in the hands of Monsignore Bernardo Nardo (President of the Postulate for the Capucin Friars,) although S. de Ricci locates the catacomb below a "Vigna Mora": s.v. "Paleography" *The Jewish Encyclopedia*, vol. 9, 1901, p. 471. A government report from 1895 notes that Ernesto Nathan, an Anglo-Italian Jew and future mayor of Rome, was negotiating with F. Barnabei for its expropriation (ACS, AA. BB. AA., 2a vers. 2a ser., b. 421, fasc. 4660). Muller laments the "deplorable" loss or destruction of artifacts from the Vigna Randanini site in *Il cimitero degli ebrei posto sulla via Portuense*, *Dissertazione della Pontificia Accademia Romana d'Archeologia Ser. II*, v. 12 (1915), p. 240

¹⁹ Reference in *JJWE* 2.360. Goodenough writes that he witnessed water streaming from the ceiling into cubiculum n. 13 in 1951 while the fields were being irrigated overhead: *Jewish Symbols in the Greco-Roman Period 2*, Princeton & New York, 1953, pp. 20-21.

grounds, as the Pontifical Commission for Sacred Archaeology has been doing for decades for the catacombs in its control.

Laurenzi's study of the catacomb's topography in chapter two is enhanced by unpublished photographs and maps from the archives of the Soprintendenza Archeologica di Roma (fig. 7 & 10), as well as by many taken by the author herself to document key structural features in the site (fig. 11-15 & 17-21).²⁰ The labeling of the different areas in fig. 7 on p. 30 seeks to conform as much as possible to what is already published. Of course, any discussion of the catacomb's evolution remains inconclusive as long as a single entrance (M) is in use, and that a serious researcher like Laurenzi could be denied permission to study the other still-extant stairway into area A (Aa) is beyond comprehension.²¹ Yet perhaps it is for this reason that Laurenzi remains overly cautious and dependent on already-published accounts, in the sense that while her work provides a close site description – greatly needed! – a number of omissions are made. Aside from not including the third skylight in front of cubiculum n. 13, noted above, the description of the exterior area M on pp. 43-46 does not include the presence of a second niche on the northern wall in M1, and that this surface was later covered by a wall of tuff blocks punctured by two arched niches on a larger scale than those in the other areas of M.²² These details are explicit in the visual and textual documentation from the 1860's, but were lost in a strangely conceived restoration of many of the surviving walls.²³

In a short list of clarifications, we also note that area C is still accessible, although only a short tract is at a lower level, and that the short, interconnected galleries on its southern edge are part of a quarry, in which few loculi are found. Contrary to what is stated on p. 38, there are at least three kokhim in area B, although cut in a different fashion from those in A and D, and, as regards to the kokhim in area D, none appear to have the extensions that Laurenzi describes on p. 40 (more of a characteristic of those in area A). The isolated cubiculum in gallery E1 (p. 40) connects to a gallery at an upper level now filled with large chunks of structural debris: the 2007 plan on p. 28 (fig. 6) documents this quite clearly. Another feature in this area also worthy of note is that E2 ultimately connects to a second quarry, in which no burials are found. In sum, there is more to the catacomb's layout than what is mentioned in this text.

The third chapter on "Pitture" provides a very detailed and accurate description of the four painted chambers in the catacomb, including information on their chronology, subject matter and design. Accompanied by a large number of photographs and drawings, references to domestic as well as funerary art, and clear topographical indications on the principal site map (p. 30), this study reveals all of Laurenzi's strengths as an art historian. With a penchant for putting topography before all other types of

²⁰ The catacomb map that Laurenzi publishes for the first time in her text on p. 30 (fig. 7) is by the architect M. Ferracuti for the Soprintendenza Archeologica di Roma. She also includes on p. 29 (fig. 6), the 2007 plan of the site by the speleologist association "Roma Sotteranea", which is more useful in terms of its documentation of the peripheral areas (especially Aa) and indication of structural features such as quarries, blocked galleries and kokhim.

²¹ Laurenzi notes on p. 36 that entrance Aa has been closed for many years.

²² Laurenzi reiterates on pp. 38-39, n. 24 that no shafts are found in this zone. G. Tomassetti, *La campagna romana*, 2, Florence, 1979, p. 79, notes these niches as already restored by 1910.

²³ As apparent in the Parker photograph of ca. 1868 published by Laurenzi on p. 43, fig. 16, and in the description of this outer area by Herzog, 1861, p. 92 & Garrucci, *Il Cimitero degli antichi ebrei scoperto recentemente in Vigna Randanini*, Rome, 1862, p. 5.

information, I would only venture that the kokhim in cubiculum 16 (discovered in 1862, not 1859 as stated on p. 55) might be part of an original phase: they are cut in a very different fashion from the kokhim in areas A and D (p. 61). Even if they prove to be a later addition, they are nonetheless arranged in a way to resemble other “loculi a forno” in the catacombs of Rome designed on a monumental scale. It is unfortunate that past restorations have left thick strata of mortar around the lids of these tombs, so that the original manner in which they were cut has been obscured. I am also not sure that the kokh at left descends below the floor level, as Laurenzi states on p. 36. On the subject matter depicted on the wall panel above these two tombs, of which only traces of the upper area survive, Laurenzi remains neutral, although others have seen in the figure of a man flanked by two trees and an equal number of horses an allusion to Orpheus, or an Orpheus/David (or even a Good Shepherd).²⁴ Her overall interpretation of the decorative scheme (pp. 57-58, nn. 31-33), is that of the soul’s journey from earth into paradise, and she dates the technique of its execution to between 190 and 220/30 (pp. 65-66).

Painted chamber 16 in a watercolor by W. Ewing for J. H. Parker ca. 1868 (n. 1160).

The final chapter, on “Materiali”, is a catalogue of artifacts, namely sarcophagi, inscriptions and miscellaneous small finds, with new photographs and current bibliographies for each piece. The last-mentioned items are those most poorly documented from the relentlessly non-stratigraphic 19th century digging, and thus it is worth adding that the imprints of at least two objects are still seen in the mortar around some opened loculi in the lower registers of corridor F2 (that said, my memory might not be

exact: it could be E2). In all probability, these are the ones mentioned by Garrucci as the impressions of a small vase and a

plate (Laurenzi, p. 68, nn. 12-13). At present, however, they might be covered up by dirt fill, which seems to migrate through the site with visitor traffic. Little else is visible of the many lamps recorded in the official site reports, and without the distinctive Jewish markings such as the menorah, they might now be very hard to trace.²⁵ Laurenzi also notes (p. 67, n. 3), that the fragments of pottery, mosaic, tile, and painted plaster seen in debris from the site (notably near the original exits) are “erratic” deposits, unlikely to relate to the specific places in which they are now found.

²⁴ Laurenzi, 2013, p. 61, n. 41. Given the very partial conservation of this panel in the 1860’s, as recorded by W. Ewing and C. Smeaton for J. H. Parker (*op. cit.* in Laurenzi, 2013, p. 94), the backsides of sheep could have been mistaken for those of horses.

²⁵ The singular object of clay incised with Jewish motifs described by Laurenzi on pp. 67-68 is now missing: Garrucci, 1865, p. 15, originally thought it to be the base of a clay lamp, but later claims to have seen similar examples in Ostia identified as *incensieri*, or thuribles.

The section on sarcophagi includes two pieces (JIWE 2.535 & 619) found in the area of the via Appia in the 18th century (although there is nothing to link the Randanini to that zone before the late 1850's). Laurenzi correctly excludes the controversial JIWE 2.556 from this list: still on display in the "Palazzo Rondinini", it was previously in another Roman family collection.²⁶

It is troubling to read in note 33 on p. 72 that the whereabouts of the fragment that I was able to photograph and identify in 2001 as part of the front panel of the sarcophagus now on display in Berlin (pp. 71-73, n. 49) are presently unknown.

For the record, additional pieces of the strigillated front panels of sarcophagus n. 50 were also identified in 2001. This sarcophagus, found virtually intact in 1859, remains *in situ*, but was damaged at some point in the late 19th or early 20th

century, and then again over the course of the latter so that all parts of the front panel are now missing. Why vandals would want to repeatedly damage this particular item, with no traces of any Jewish iconography or inscriptions, is far from apparent: the images themselves are stock material, not even "personalized" with portraits of the deceased.²⁷

There are some photographs and descriptions of other sarcophagi still in the catacomb, to which a small number of archival and bibliographic clarifications – none of any great significance - could be made. The "sarcofago del cubicolo 9" (n. 55) is not, strictly speaking, an unpublished piece, although Laurenzi should be credited with the first thorough examination of its form.²⁸ The "sarcofago fittile" in an arched niche in area M does not necessarily come from the site: a clay sarcophagus, already broken, was found in another part of the vineyard in 1885.²⁹ In addition, while the item in question appears to fit the niche in which it is now displayed, it should be emphasized that the niche is a modern one, made on a larger scale than those originally constructed in area M.³⁰ Laurenzi is preparing a more extensive catalogue of the marble fragments now

²⁶ In the description of CIJ 1.1 on pp. 70-71, n. 24, it would be helpful to reference *Marmi antichi del palazzo Rondinini* ed. M. Bertinetti & D. Candilio, Rome, 2011, pp. 216-219.

²⁷ Laurenzi, 2013, p. 75, n. 46.

²⁸ Bibliography in JIWE 2, p. 179 (iii); also mentioned by O. Marucchi, *Breve guida al cimitero giudaico di Vigna Randanini*, Rome, 1884, p. 18.

²⁹ G. Fiorelli, *Notizie degli Scavi d'Antichita'*, 1885, p. 77

³⁰ JIWE 2, p. 175, provides measurements of the piece. H. J. Leon, in *The Jews of Ancient Rome*, 2d ed., Peabody, MA, 1995, pp. 56-57, fig. 5, describes the presence of several clay sarcophagi in the restored niches of area M, recesses "somewhat larger" than the original ones, whose measurements he also provides.

conserved in chamber H (p. 71 n. 26 & p. 73, n. 38).³¹ To these could be added the many artifacts removed from the site in the late 19th and 20th centuries that are, for the most part, in the storerooms of the Museo Nazionale Romano (few are likely to have come from inside the catacomb, given the government's express prohibition against removing material from the site, but would nonetheless provide a broader perspective on the necropolis *sub divo*). Others I note briefly in my 2001 report from the site.³²

The last part of this chapter summarizes the main characteristics of the nearly 200 Jewish inscriptions recovered from the site, although with the Greek transliterated into the Roman alphabet. Perhaps because a new catalogue of these pieces is in process, Laurenzi's discussion remains a survey of the most striking words and phrases.³³

The bibliography contains nearly all of the essential sources on the Vigna Randanini catacomb, along with studies of painting, sculpture and the very latest in research on the Monteverde site. Somewhat problematic, however, is that not all the works are explicitly cited or incorporated into the text.³⁴ A few other studies that might have been helpful to reference I mentioned above, or in my citations, to which could be added – if only to enrich one's understanding of the rich topographical data from this zone – Ilaria Bignamini and Amanda Claridge's article on the Tomb of Claudia Semne (with a catacomb plan superimposed onto the vineyard grounds) and Lucrezia Spera's 2004 study of the nearby catacombs of Pretestato (*Praetextatus*).³⁵

As noted in Claudio Procaccia's introduction, this detailed and informative overview will serve as a guide for future investigations into the catacomb's excavation and contents, as well as on the discovery, restoration and analysis of the site. Many pieces of these puzzles still exist, but need re-assembling. It is exciting to take stock of the work in the Vigna Randanini catacomb up to this point as illustrated in Laurenzi's text, and focus on what needs a clearer resolution. Now is the time to move beyond the manifest, and make bold and interpretive analyses of the site.

³¹ Marucchi, 1884, p. 5, describes a sarcophagus fragment with “genietti di caccia ed arieti”.

³² Laurenzi, 2013, p. 92.

³³ S. Lombardi, *La catacomba ebraica di Vigna Randanini, Forma Urbis* (2009), p. 14. This is a section that needs further development: for example, Laurenzi calls *JIWE* 2.224 “exceptional” from its mention of a proselyte: yet it should be noted that other inscriptions from the *VR* (*JIWE* 2 nn. 218 & 392) also use this term.

³⁴ This might very well have been an editorial decision: nonetheless, it leaves the work somewhat incomplete. To give just one example, the description of area M on pp. 46-47 fails to indicate that Garrucci almost immediately retracted his identification of this space as a synagogue, as we read in his *Osservazioni intorno al “Cimitero degli antichi ebrei, in Dissertazioni archeologiche di vario argomento, 2, Rome, 1865, pp. 150-151.*

³⁵ I. Bignamini & A. Claridge, *The Tomb of Claudia Semne and Excavations in Eighteenth Century Rome in Papers of the British School at Rome, Vol. 66* (1998), pp. 215-244. Spera's work is *Il complesso di Pretestato sulla Via Appia: storia topografica e monumentale di un insediamento funerario paleocristiano nel suburbio di Roma, Vatican City, 2004.*